

Determination of rare earth elements and yttrium in zircons by plasma emission spectrometry after solvent extraction separation of zirconium with di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid

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Abstract : A simple and rapid inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometric (ICP-OES) determination of trace level rare earth elements (REEs) and Y in high purity zirconium matrix and zircon samples is described. The method involves solvent extraction separation of zirconium from 3 M HCl solution using di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D₂EHPA) in toluene, which selectively separates zirconium leaving behind the trace REEs and Y in aqueous media, for quantification by ICP-OES. The quantitative extraction of Tm, Yb and Lu are achieved by the addition of octanol. The method has been applied to synthetic zirconium samples doped with REEs and Y and the recoveries were quantitative. The method was extended to the determination of REEs and Y zircon samples. Accuracy of the method was checked by applying the proposed method to three zircon certified reference materials and the percentage error obtained was 1-6%. The values obtained agreed well with the reported values. The percentage RSD of all estimated elements varied between 1-5% at different concentration levels.

Keywords : Tm, Yb, Li, di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid, ICP-OES.

Introduction

The element zircon occurs widely in lithosphere (0.02 percent) with approximately 130 mg/kg within the earth's crust¹. Zirconium exists in more than 140 recognised mineral species including Zircon (ZrSiO₄) and Beddeleyite (ZrO₂)¹. Zircon with a zirconium content of approximately 64% is the main source of zirconium. Zircon is an accessory mineral found in a wide range of igneous, metamorphic and sedimentary rocks. It is a refractory mineral that generally survives weathering and transport and is a common component of heavy mineral suites in sedimentary rocks. The refractory nature of zircon which allows preservation of age information should also allow the preservation of other trace element characteristics. Zircons that grew in different geological environment should have different trace element signatures. Rare earth element (REE) data in zircons were used to provide information on nature of the source region of sedimentary rocks².

Zirconium alloys are extensively used in the nuclear industry as cladding material for nuclear fuel, mainly due to its low thermal neutron capture cross section, their

high mechanical strength and resistance to corrosion at high temperatures. Rare earth elements especially Gd, Sm, Dy and Eu are strong neutron absorbers and act as neutron poisons. Their concentration in the nuclear materials needs to be maintained below a critical level. Hence the determination of trace level rare earth elements in high purity nuclear grade zirconium is very important.

In view of the above application in geochemistry and nuclear industry it has become necessary to develop new and improved methodologies for the accurate and precise determination of rare earth elements in zircon. Various instrumental analytical techniques have been utilized for the determination of REEs in zircon. Inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)¹, inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)^{3,4}, laser ablation-inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS)⁵, electro thermal vaporization-inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ETV-ICP-MS)⁶, instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA)², ion microprobe⁷, isotope dilution mass spectrometry (ID-MS)⁸ etc. are some techniques used for the determination of

REEs in zircon. ICP-OES has been established as a preferred technique for the determination of REE due to its simplicity, wide dynamic range, adequate sensitivity, good precision, multi element capability and high sample throughput. However the direct determination of trace REEs in zirconium matrix by ICP-OES is not successful due to spectral interferences caused by line rich emission of Zr. Separation of REEs from the major zirconium matrix is essential for the accurate determination of REEs. Cation exchange chromatography^{9,10} is widely used for the group separation of trace level lanthanides from majority of the geological matrix elements. But Zr shows multiple elution peaks in ion exchange method using both 8 M HCl and 6 N HNO₃¹¹ and a minor portion of Zr comes in the REE fraction. The accompanied Zr becomes very high at higher quantities of Zr in the matrix and it affects the REE determination by ICP-OES. The other separation procedures used for lanthanides are precipitation of REEs as oxalate¹² or fluoride¹³ using calcium as carrier, solvent extraction using bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphate¹⁴ and mixture of bis(2-ethylhexyl)phosphate and mono(2-ethylhexyl)dihydrogen phosphate¹⁵.

In the present study, REEs are separated from Zr by extraction of zirconium into di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D₂EHPA) in toluene. D₂EHPA is a good extractant for REE, Y, Sc, U, Th, Zr, Ti and Fe¹⁶. However, at very high acid concentration of the aqueous phase, extraction of REEs is negligible. There are reports on the separation of REEs from reactor grade uranium¹⁷ and thorium matrix¹⁸ by extracting major matrix elements uranium and thorium into di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D₂EHPA) in toluene. This communication enumerates the studies carried out for the separation REEs from major zirconium matrix by the extraction of Zr into 30% (v/v) di-(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid (D₂EHPA) in toluene from 3 M HCl solution and its application in the determination of REEs in zircon samples.

Experimental

Instrumentation : A Jobin Yvon model 2000(2) sequential ICP-AES from M/s Jobin Yvon, France was used. The instrumental parameters used are given in Table 1. The spectral lines used in the study, back ground equivalent concentrations (BEC) and detection limits (DLs) obtained are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Operating parameters for ICP-AES system

RF Generator	40.68 MHz (crystal controlled)
Forward power	1000 W
Reflected power	< 5 W
Gas flow	10.5 L min ⁻¹ coolant 0.3 L min ⁻¹ auxillary
Monochromator	Modified Czerny Turner
Focal length	640 mm
Diffraction grating	4320 grooves mm ⁻¹
Ruled area	110 mm × 80 mm
Wavelength range	170–440 nm
Dispersion	0.005 nm mm ⁻¹ (first order)
Nebulizer	Meinhard nebulizer
Solution uptake rate	1.0 ml min ⁻¹
Slits	21 μm entrance slit and 22 μm exit slit
Detector	Photomultiplier R-106
No. of steps and time	15 steps, 0.2 s
Observation height	11 mm above load coil

Table 2. Spectral lines used for emission measurement of REE and Y BEC, L/B and D.L. values

Element	Wavelength (nm)	BEC ^a (μg/ml)	L/B	D.L. ^b (μg/ml)
La	333.749	0.141	14.1	0.0042
La	398.852	0.161	12.4	0.0048
Ce	418.660	0.296	6.76	0.0088
Ce	413.765	0.335	5.97	0.0100
Pr	422.293	0.362	1.66	0.0109
Nd	430.358	0.271	7.39	0.0081
Sm	442.434	0.155	3.87	0.0046
Eu	381.967	0.022	9.12	0.0006
Gd	342.247	0.154	12.9	0.0046
Tb	350.917	0.168	3.57	0.0050
Dy	353.170	0.058	8.67	0.0017
Ho	345.600	0.106	5.67	0.0032
Er	349.910	0.123	4.88	0.0037
Tm	346.220	0.073	8.18	0.0022
Yb	328.937	0.014	14.6	0.0004
Lu	261.542	0.012	16.2	0.0004
Y	371.030	0.041	24.5	0.0012

^aBEC is calculated from : Concentration (μg/ml) $I_b/(I_p - I_b)$, where I_p and I_b represents peak counts and background counts respectively.

^bD.L. is calculated based on three times the standard deviation of the blank at 1% RSD, (DL = BEC × 0.03).

Reagents : All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical or guaranteed reagent grade. High purity rare

earth oxide (Johnson Matthey, UK) was used for the preparation of the standard solutions.

Di-(2-ethylhexyl)hydrogen phosphate (D₂EHPA) (Spectrochem, India) was used as 30% solution in toluene and equilibrated with 3 M HCl solution (equal volume).

1-Octanol (Spectrochem, India) was used in the experiment.

Preparation of standards : A stock solution of 1000 µg mL⁻¹ each was prepared from rare earth oxides by dissolving in hydrochloric acid solution, the acidity was maintained at 1 M HCl. 5 ml of 1000 µg mL⁻¹ of all rare earth elements were diluted to 100 ml to obtain 50 µg mL⁻¹ solution maintaining 0.5 M HCl.

For the preparation of synthetic standards high purity zirconium oxychloride was used.

Sample decomposition :

Two sample decomposition procedures were adopted for dissolution of zircon samples.

Sodium peroxide fusion method :

A 0.2 g sample (-200 mesh) was fused with 5 g sodium peroxide in a nickel crucible and cooled melt was dissolved in dilute 5% (v/v) HCl and boiled for 15 min. Ammonia precipitation was carried out in presence of ammonium chloride; the precipitate was filtered through a Whatman 541 filter paper. The precipitate was washed with 5% (v/v) NH₄OH in 1% (w/v) NH₄Cl and transferred to the same beaker and dissolved in 50 ml of 3 M HCl.

Fluoride fusion method :

0.2 g of the sample was mixed with 2.5 g flux (a homogenous mixture of KHF₂ and NaF in 3 : 1 ratio) in a platinum crucible and fused to red hot over a burner. The crucible was cooled, 10 ml 1 : 1 sulphuric acid was added and heated on a hot plate till the evolution of sulphur dioxide fumes to ensure the complete removal of fluoride. The contents were cooled and transferred into a beaker with 5 ml of concentrated HCl and boiled for 15 min. Ammonia precipitation was carried out in presence of ammonium chloride; the precipitate was filtered through a Whatman 541 filter paper. The precipitate was washed with 5% (v/v) NH₄OH in 1% (w/v) NH₄Cl and transferred to the same beaker and dissolved in 50 ml of 3 M HCl.

Solvent extraction :

The sample solution in 3 M HCl was transferred into a 125 ml separating funnel and added pre-equilibrated 25 ml of 30% (v/v) bis(2-ethylhexyl)hydrogen phosphate (HDEHP) in toluene and 5 ml octanol and shaken for 5 min. The two phases were allowed to separate. The organic phase is discarded. The aqueous phase is filtered through a Whatman filter paper 540 and heated over water bath to incipient dryness. The residue was dissolved in 5 ml of 1 : 1 HCl and made up to 50 ml.

Results and discussion

Investigation of spectral interferences :

The major zirconium matrix in zircon alter physical properties of the plasma by introducing high total dissolved salts which in turn cause the suppression of emission lines of rare earth elements. The line rich spectra of zirconium cause serious spectral interferences mostly additive in nature. The interference effect of zirconium on REE lines were studied by using solution containing known trace amount of REEs and Y and 50, 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000 µg/ml of zirconium. The most commonly used sensitive and relative interference free lines are selected for study. Above 1 mg/ml zirconium concentration, all the studied lines showed suppression to varied extent. Study also reveals Ce (418.660), La (398.852), Lu (261.542), Nd (430.357), Ho (345.600) and Tb (350.917) suffer spectral interferences from zirconium lines. Severe interference was observed in the case of Ce (418.660), Ho (345.600) and Tb (350.917) even at very low concentration of Zr. Thus it is clear from the above studies that ICP-AES determination of REEs in presence of high amount of Zr gives erroneous results and separation of Zr from REEs prior to their estimation is necessary.

Solvent extraction :

In the present technique, separation of zirconium by solvent extraction was studied in different acidity with respect to HCl. Synthetic aqueous mixture was prepared by mixing 50 µg each of REEs and 100 mg of Zr in 50 ml solution maintaining different acidic conditions (0.5 M, 1 M, 2 M, 3 M, 4 M, 6 M HCl). These synthetic mixtures were extracted into a mixture of 25 ml 30% (v/v) D₂EHPA in toluene and 5 ml *n*-octanol. The aqueous

layer was separated and estimated for REE content. Extraction of zirconium was quantitative in the all acidities. But the maximum recovery of REEs especially HREEs were observed in 3 M HCl medium. The addition of octanol during the extraction is essential as it facilitates quantitative recovery of HREEs especially Tm, Yb and Lu. In the absence of octanol recoveries of Tm, Yb and Lu were 85%, 75% and 62% respectively. The recoveries were improved ~90% by the addition of octanol.

Concentration of D₂EHPA was optimized by extracting synthetic mixture into 25 ml of 10%–50% of D₂EHPA in toluene. Quantitative removal of zirconium was observed 30% D₂EHPA and above. The procedure is further optimized in respect of contact time. Optimisation of shaking time was carried out by shaking the synthetic mixture with a mixture of 25 ml 30% (v/v) D₂EHPA in toluene and 5 ml *n*-octanol for 3 to 5 min time. Residual Zr present in the aqueous phase was very less for 5 min shaking time. Two times extraction of 5 min duration was quantitatively removing Zr from the aqueous layer. But the recovery of elements Tm, Yb, Lu and Y was low after second extraction. Hence only one time extraction was carried out. The amount of Zr remaining in the aqueous phase after one extraction was below 5 µg/ml which

was not affecting the ICP-OES determination of REEs. Under the optimized conditions of 5 min contact time, D₂EHPA concentration 30%, 3 M HCl concentration in aqueous phase and presence of octanol gave maximum separation of REEs from zirconium matrix.

Two synthetic standards containing 100 mg of Zr was prepared by doping known amounts of REEs in the range 0.5 µg/ml to 1 µg/ml and extracted into 30% (v/v) D₂EHPA in toluene and result obtained are listed in Table 3. Quantitative recoveries were obtained in both the cases.

The method was extended to the determination of REEs in zircon samples. Zircon samples were decomposed by fluoride fusion and sodium peroxide fusion. Fluoride fusion was selected in preference to the sodium peroxide fusion. Silica introduced in the sample solution by the fusion of zircon samples with sodium peroxide makes the phase separation very difficult. The residual Zr is about 10% and it affects emission lines of rare earth elements. But during the sulphuric acid fuming after the fluoride fusion, the silica present in the sample is removed as silicon fluoride completely and hence no interference from silica during the extraction stage was observed. The major elements introduced during the fusion stage are removed by ammonia-ammonium hydroxide precipitation.

Table 3. Analytical results of REEs and Y in synthetic Zr samples (values in µg/ml) by D₂EHPA extraction

Element	Synthetic mixture I			Synthetic mixture II		
	Amount Added	Amount Found	Recovery (%)	Amount Added	Amount Found	Recovery (%)
La	0.50	0.50	100	1.0	1.05	105
Ce	0.50	0.50	100	1.0	1.0	100
Pr	0.50	0.49	98	1.0	0.98	98
Nd	0.50	0.50	100	1.0	1.0	100
Sm	0.50	0.49	98	1.0	0.97	97
Eu	0.50	0.50	100	1.0	1.0	100
Gd	0.50	0.49	98	1.0	0.97	97
Tb	0.50	0.49	98	1.0	0.96	96
Dy	0.50	0.49	98	1.0	0.98	98
Ho	0.50	0.48	96	1.0	0.95	95
Er	0.50	0.48	96	1.0	0.95	95
Tm	0.50	0.44	88	1.0	0.89	89
Yb	0.50	0.43	86	1.0	0.88	88
Lu	0.50	0.43	86	1.0	0.87	87
Y	0.50	0.48	96	1.0	0.95	95

Synthetic standard I and II are prepared by known amount of analyte to 100 mg zirconium and analysed after processing the solution by proposed method. The results presented are average of three values.

Table 4. Determination of REEs and Y in zircon reference materials BGS IGS 35, CERAM 2 CAS 15 and BCS CRM 388

Element	BGS IGS 35		CERAM 2 CAS 15		BCS CRM 388	
	Reported ^a (µg/ml)	Found (µg/ml)	Reported ^a (µg/ml)	Found (µg/ml)	Reported ^a (µg/ml)	Found (µg/ml)
La	82.2	80.5	41.2	40.3	30	30.8
Ce	183	175	100.7	97.8	80	79
Pr	19.8	20.0	10.5	9.9	-	19.9
Nd	77.2	74.0	40.7	38.8	40	37.5
Sm	19.4	18.2	13.1	12.3	10	9.2
Eu	2.84	2.75	2.3	2.25	-	3.35
Gd	33.1	34.5	26.1	26.7	-	36.5
Tb	10.0	9.3	8.3	7.5	-	10.5
Dy	103.4	100.3	85.9	82.9	-	110
Ho	33.6	32.0	28.0	27.6	-	34.1
Er	141.8	141	119.7	120.3	-	152
Tm	28.9	27	24.9	23.6	-	31
Yb	283.2	265	200	186	300	281
Lu	51.0	45.8	41.0	38.0	-	53.2
Y	1005	964	912	873	1071	1001

^aValues reported by Perkins *et al.*⁴. ^bValues reported by Singh *et al.*³. ^cBureau of analysed samples Ltd., Newham Hall, Middlesbrough, UK. Revised certificate, October 1992. ^dAll values are mean of n=3 replicates.

Three zircon reference samples BGS IGS 35, CERAM 2 CAS 15 and BCS CRM 388 were analysed for their REE content by the proposed method and result obtained are given in Table 4. Certified values for the concentration of these elements are not available. However, the concentrations of these elements have been reported by Singh *et al.*³ for CERAM 2 CAS 15, Perkin *et al.*⁴ for BGS IGS 35 and Gregoire *et al.*⁶ BCS CRM 388 (selected elements). The result obtained by the proposed solvent extraction group separation of REEs and Y are in good agreement with reported values. Relative standard deviation ranging from 1 to 5% was obtained for the studied elements at different concentration levels.

Conclusion

ICP-AES determination of traces of REEs and Y is not possible in presence of large quantity of zirconium. A simple, and rapid solvent extraction separation of REE and Y from dominant Zr matrix is achieved using 30% D₂EDPA in toluene. The solution after separation is suitable for spectral interference free ICP-AES measurement. Though the heavy REEs like Er, Tm, Yb and Lu are partially extracted to D₂EDPA, their extraction is pre-

vented by the addition of 5 ml of octanol. The addition of octanol does not affect the extraction behavior of zirconium. This method was extended to the determination of REEs and Y in zircon samples. The accuracy of the proposed method was checked by analyzing three international reference materials. The values obtained by the present study agreed well with these reported values.

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